

INSURANCE OF INVESTMENT PROJECTS AND THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Abstract

This study addresses the role of insurance in investment projects, with a particular focus on international insurance companies and the specific insurance products, they offer for the investment projects worldwide. The study analyzes the importance of insurance as a risk management mechanism, its impact on promoting foreign direct investment, insurance alternatives at different stages of projects, and the ways in which insurance companies channel their funds into financial markets and especially in the insurance market.

It also examines the role of investments in the economy as a whole, the challenges related to regulation, financial stability and sustainable economic and financial development. The paper also addresses the risks covered by insurance of investment projects and their consequences, emphasizing the crucial role of available insurance products in their reduction and coverage.

The analysis is based on academic literature and national and international institutional reports (Rejda & McNamara, 2017; World Bank, 2021, etc.).

Keywords: investment projects, insurance, risk management, investment policies, international companies

Introduction

Our country, with its strategic location, positioned in Southeastern Europe, promises a dynamic and growing economic development, ready for foreign and domestic investments. Over the last decade, the country has undertaken important reforms to create a business-friendly environment, making it an attractive destination for foreign investors. With its competitive tax policies, expanding infrastructure and skilled workforce, Albania presents a multitude of opportunities for businesses seeking to establish a base in the region.

In the conditions of economic globalization and increasing international competition, investment projects face numerous financial, political and operational risks. Insurance of investment projects represents an essential instrument for protecting capital and ensuring the financial sustainability of investors (Dorfman & Carther, 2013). International companies, which operate in different economic and legal environments, increasingly rely on insurance mechanisms to minimize uncertainties.

On the other hand, insurance companies are not only risk bearers, but also important institutional investors. They manage significant financial funds, which are invested in various financial instruments and economic projects, directly affecting economic development.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the relationship between insurance and insurance companies, evaluating the type of project insurance, risks covered by the projects insurance and their impact on financial decision-making, also the benefits of insurance of the national and international projects for investors.

Objectives

The main objectives of the study are:

a) To analyze the role of insurance in investment projects.

b) To examine the importance of insurance by international companies.

c) To provide suggestions on how different investment projects can be insured, based on the specific risks to which they are exposed.

Study Methodology

The study is based on qualitative and quantitative methodologies. Theoretical analysis, scientific literature review, financial reports, and comparative analysis of insurance companies' practices at the international level are used. This is accompanied by concrete practical examples. The study also includes statistical data obtained from official information sources in Albania and beyond.

Literature Review

Economic and financial literature emphasizes that insurance helps transfer risk and increases the credibility of projects towards investors and financial institutions (Rejda & McNamara, 2017; Dorfman & Carther, 2013). Investment project insurance functions as a financial mechanism for protecting capital and guaranteeing project continuity in the event of natural, technical or financial risks (Rejda & McNamara, 2017). Risk analysis and management are essential for capital-intensive projects, as they directly affect the net present value and the rate of return on investment (Dorfman & Carther, 2013). Investment project insurance aims to cover financial losses that may arise during the project life cycle, from planning to operation.

The main types of insurance include construction insurance (CAR/EAR), property insurance, civil liability and business interruption insurance. These instruments contribute to increasing the financial sustainability of projects (Dorfman & Carther, 2013).

According to the risk management theory, insurance serves as a mechanism for transferring risk from

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the investor to specialized institutions, reducing financial and operational uncertainties (Doherty, 2000). Various studies argue that the presence of insurance significantly increases the guarantee of project implementation and consider insurance as a basic condition for protecting invested capital (OECD, 2018). According to the literature, insurance companies provide advanced insurance and reinsurance products, enabling global risk distribution (Swiss Re, 2022).

A significant part of the literature focuses on the role of insurance companies as long-term institutional investors. Due to the nature of their liabilities (long-term insurance policies), insurance companies tend to invest in financial instruments with long maturities and relatively stable returns (European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority, 2021).

Also, according to international literature, the increased interest of insurance companies themselves in economic investment alternatives is highlighted, especially in conditions of low interest rates. According to studies by the (World Bank, 2017), investments in infrastructure, renewable energy and sustainable projects offer opportunities for long-term returns and financial stability.

1. Insurance and investment projects

1.1 Definition of investment project insurance

Investment project insurance represents an important financial protection mechanism, which aims to cover losses and damages that may occur throughout the life of an investment project, from the planning phase to the operation phase (Doherty, 2000). Essentially, insurance functions as a form of risk transfer, where the investor or project developer passes the financial consequences of certain risks to the insurance company in return for the payment of an insurance premium (Doherty, 2000; OECD, 2018).

This type of insurance is particularly important for projects with high financial value and increased risk, such as construction, infrastructure, industrial or energy projects. Such projects involve large capital investments, long implementation periods and complex technical processes, which significantly increase exposure to natural, technical, financial and legal risks. In the absence of insurance, these risks can lead to significant financial losses or even project failure.

From a financial perspective, investment project insurance contributes to the stability and economic viability of the project, guaranteeing its continuity even in the event of unforeseen events. It also serves as a guarantee instrument for banks and financial institutions, which often require insurance as a condition for granting loans or long-term financing.

At the same time, insurance also provides security for other parties involved in the project, such as contractors, subcontractors and consultants, by clearly defining responsibilities and coverage of damages. For this reason, investment project insurance should not be seen simply as an additional cost, but as a strategic element of risk management and a key factor for the long-term success of the project.

1.2 Project phases and the relevant insurance

Investment projects develop in several interconnected phases, each of which is characterized by different types of risks. For this reason, project insurance is not the same at each stage, but is adapted according to the nature of the activity and the level of risk exposure. Proper insurance management at each stage contributes directly to the success and sustainability of the project.

a) Planning phase

The planning phase constitutes the basis on which the entire project is built and plays a crucial role in determining the risks and the need for insurance. In this phase, the main preliminary analyses that affect the financial and organizational structure of the project are carried out.

Risk analysis is a systematic process for identifying, assessing and classifying potential risks that may arise during the implementation of the project. These risks can be technical, financial, legal, environmental or organizational. The purpose of risk analysis is to determine the probability of each risk occurring and its potential financial impact, serving as a basis for decision-making on insurance.

The feasibility study analyzes whether the project is feasible from a technical, economic and financial point of view. This study helps to identify the main risks related to costs, deadlines and return on investment. The results of the feasibility study directly influence the determination of the types of insurance needed and the level of coverage.

The determination of the need for insurance is carried out at this stage by deciding which risks should be transferred to the insurance company and which can be managed by the investor himself. This includes the selection of the types of insurance, the amount of coverage and the insurance period. At this stage, professional liability insurance for designers and consultants is often also required.

b) Construction phase

The construction phase is the most critical period of the project due to the high intensity of the works and the high exposure to physical and technical risks. At this stage, insurance plays a key role in protecting the project from unforeseen damages.

CAR (Contractors All Risks) insurance is a comprehensive insurance that covers the risks associated with civil construction works.

EAR (Erection All Risks) insurance is mainly applied to industrial and technological projects, where the focus is on the assembly and installation of mechanical and electrical equipment. At this stage, the insurance also covers physical damage, accidents and technical errors, which can be caused by human factors, technological failures or natural events. The inclusion of these coverages ensures that the project does not stop or face major financial losses.

c) Operation phase

After the completion of construction, the project enters the operation phase, where full operation and revenue generation begin. Although physical risks are

reduced compared to the construction phase, they do not disappear, but take on other forms.

Property insurance protects project assets, such as buildings, equipment and machinery, from physical damage that may occur during daily use. This insurance ensures the preservation of the value of the investment and minimizes capital losses.

Business interruption insurance covers financial losses that arise as a result of the interruption or limitation of activity due to an insured loss. This insurance is particularly important for projects that depend on uninterrupted operation to generate income.

Civil liability insurance covers bodily or material damage that the project may cause to third parties during operation. It provides legal and financial protection against possible claims and lawsuits, providing stability and security for the investor.

1.3 Main types of project insurance

Investment projects involve a wide range of risks, which vary according to the project phase, the nature of the activity and the value of the investment. For this reason, project insurance is not limited to a single type of insurance, but is realized through a combined insurance package, which aims at complete financial and operational protection. The main types of insurance for investment projects are as follows:

a) Construction and assembly insurance (CAR/EAR)

Construction and assembly insurance represents the basis of insurance for investment projects during the physical implementation phase of the project.

- CAR (Contractors All Risks) It includes physical damage to the object under construction, materials, equipment and machinery used on the site. This insurance also covers damages that may be caused to third parties as a result of construction works. CAR is considered essential for infrastructure and construction projects, as it offers broad coverage against unforeseen risks.

- EAR (Erection All Risks). This insurance is usually used in industrial, energy and technological projects, where the installation of complex equipment constitutes one of the most dangerous phases of the project. EAR covers damages resulting from assembly errors, technical defects and accidents during installation.

b) Property insurance (buildings, equipment, machinery)

Property insurance is one of the most important forms of insurance during the project operation phase. It aims to protect the physical assets of the project, including buildings, equipment, machineries and supporting infrastructure.

This insurance covers damages that may be caused by natural hazards, fire, explosions, accidental damage and other unforeseen events. The main purpose of property insurance is to preserve the value of the investment and prevent capital losses that may negatively affect the financial viability of the project.

c) Civil liability insurance

Civil liability insurance aims to protect the project and the parties involved from legal claims of third parties. This insurance covers bodily injury, material damage and financial losses that the project may cause to other persons or entities during construction or operation.

In large projects, civil liability is one of the most important risks, as a single incident can lead to high legal costs and significant damages. For this reason, civil liability insurance is often mandatory and included in construction and investment contracts.

d) Materials transportation insurance

Materials transportation insurance covers the risks associated with the movement of materials, equipment and machinery from the place of production or supply to the project site. This insurance is particularly important for projects that depend on the import of expensive equipment or international transport. It covers damage that may occur during transport due to accidents, damage, theft or adverse natural conditions. Transport insurance ensures that losses during supply do not affect the project's deadlines and costs.

e) Business interruption insurance

Business interruption insurance

The purpose of the insurance is to protect the project from indirect financial losses resulting from the interruption or limitation of activity due to an insured damage.

This insurance covers the loss of income, fixed expenses and additional costs that the project may incur during the interruption period. It is particularly important for projects that generate continuous income and where any interruption can have serious financial consequences.

1.4 Risks covered by investment project insurance

Investment projects are exposed to a wide range of risks throughout their life cycle. Identifying, assessing and covering these risks through insurance is a key element of effective project management. Project insurance aims to reduce the financial consequences of risks, ensuring stability and continuity of investment activity.

a) Natural hazards (earthquakes, floods, fires)

Natural hazards include extraordinary events caused by forces of nature and that usually have an immediate and severe financial impact. In addition to earthquakes, floods and fires, this category also includes storms, intense rainfall, landslides and extreme temperatures.

These hazards can cause:

1. damage or complete destruction of buildings under construction,
2. loss of equipment and materials
3. interruption of works for long periods,
4. increased costs for reconstruction and repair.

Insurance against natural hazards covers the repair or reconstruction of damaged assets, avoiding major capital losses and prolonged project interruptions. In

many cases, these risks are mandatory for inclusion in insurance contracts.

b) Technical and engineering risks

Technical and engineering risks are related to the technological and professional complexity of investment projects. They include design errors, incorrect engineering calculations, use of unsuitable materials, and defects during assembly or testing of equipment. These risks appear most often during the construction phase, but can also continue during the operation of the project.

The consequences of these risks are:

1. the need to revise the technical project,
2. delays in construction deadlines,
3. significant cost increases,
4. risk to the safety of employees and users of the facility.

Insurance covers the damages resulting from these problems, including repair costs and technical interventions. This allows the project to continue without long interruptions and without severe financial impacts.

c) Operational and human risks

Operational and human risks arise from the daily activity of the project and from human factors. These include accidents at work, professional errors, lack of experience, incorrect use of equipment and inefficient management. These risks are present in all phases of the project, but are particularly pronounced in phases with high work intensity.

These risks can lead to:

1. bodily injury and loss of life,
2. material damage to equipment and facilities,
3. interruption of activity,
4. legal and financial consequences for the project.

Insurance covers the financial consequences of these risks, including bodily injury, material damage and liability to third parties. In addition to the financial aspect, insurance also contributes to improving safety standards and discipline at work.

d) Financial risks (delays, loss of income)

Financial risks are related to the economic performance of the project and directly affect the return on investment. Delays in implementation, increased construction costs, lack of financing or interruption of activity can cause significant losses of planned income.

These risks include:

1. loss of expected profit,
2. difficulty in repaying loans,
3. reduced credibility with investors and banks.

Business interruption insurance and insurance for delays in starting operations help cover financial losses, ensuring stability and economic continuity for the project.

e) Legal and contractual risks

Legal and contractual risks stem from the complex relationships between parties involved in the project, such as investors, contractors, suppliers and public authorities. Failure to comply with contractual terms, conflicts between investors and contractors, and lawsuits from third parties constitute serious financial and reputational risks.

The consequences of these risks can be:

1. lengthy legal proceedings,
2. high compensation payments
3. delays in the implementation or operation of the project.

Civil liability insurance and other specific insurances provide legal and financial protection, covering damages and legal costs. This helps maintain the financial stability and credibility of project.

The data shows that construction risks account for the largest share of coverage (around 40%), as the construction phase is the most exposed to delays, technical errors and accidents, which are among the most common causes of project losses (Project Management Institute, 2023; World Bank, 2020). Financial risks rank second (25%), reflecting concerns about costs, liquidity and return on investment, as financial uncertainty and funding constraints significantly affect project continuity and performance (International Finance Corporation, 2019). Natural risks account for around 20% of coverage, since events such as earthquakes, floods and other natural catastrophes can cause substantial material damage and project interruptions, especially in infrastructure and construction investments (Swiss Re, 2022). Meanwhile, legal risks have the lowest percentage (15%), indicating that although regulatory and contractual risks are important, they are generally perceived as less frequent compared to technical and financial risks (Allianz, 2023).

1.5 Risk Analysis and Management in Investment Projects

1.5.1 The Role of Risk Analysis in Investment Projects

Investment projects constitute medium- and long-term capital commitments, which are carried out under conditions of uncertainty. For this reason, risk analysis and management are considered essential elements of the financial decision-making process. Every investment project, regardless of its size or the sector in which it is developed, is exposed to various risks that may negatively affect the achievement of financial and operational objectives. Risk analysis aims to identify sources of uncertainty and assess their potential impact, while risk management includes concrete strategies and measures to reduce, control or transfer these risks. In this context, insurance plays a key role as a financial instrument for protecting investments and ensuring economic sustainability.

- Identification of the main risks in investment projects

Identification of the main risks in investment projects constitutes the initial and most important phase of the risk management process. This process consists of

systematically identifying all possible risks that may affect the investment project throughout its life cycle.

- Financial risks in investment projects

Financial risks represent the possibility that changes in financial and macroeconomic factors will negatively affect the value of the investment, cash flows and financial sustainability of the project. In medium- and long-term investment projects, these risks are particularly important, as they are directly related to the instability of financial markets and economic conditions.

The main financial risks include:

a) Interest rate risk

Interest rate risk is related to the possibility that changes in interest rates in financial markets will negatively affect the cost of financing the project and the present value of cash flows. This risk is particularly important for projects financed through bank loans or debt instruments. Impact on investment projects, increasing the interest rate: increases the cost of debt service, reduces the profitability of the project, negatively affects financial indicators such as NPV - Net Present Value (Net Present Value) and IRR (Internal Rate of Return) (Internal Rate of Return) NPV and IRR are key instruments for the financial evaluation of investment projects. While NPV measures the real value created for the investor, IRR indicates the level of return on investment. The combination of these indicators provides a solid basis for financial decision-making, especially in high-risk projects). If the project has loans with a variable interest rate, the investor is directly exposed to this risk.

b) Currency risk

Currency risk arises from changes in the exchange rate between the domestic currency and foreign currencies. This risk is present when: the investment is financed in foreign currency, income is generated in local currency, equipment or services are imported from abroad. The financial impact of the depreciation of the local currency increases: the value of foreign currency liabilities, import costs, the financial burden of the project. While the strengthening of the local currency can reduce the competitiveness of the project in international markets. Currency risk management is achieved through: matching the currency of income with the currency of expenses, long-term foreign exchange contracts, hedging currency risk, using financial hedging instruments.

c) Liquidity risk

Liquidity risk is related to the inability of the project to meet short-term financial obligations in a timely manner, despite the fact that the project may be financially sustainable in the long term. The main causes of this risk are: delays in payments from customers, unforeseen costs, poor cash flow planning, excessive reliance on short-term financing. The consequences for the project are associated with a lack of liquidity which: increases the risk of bankruptcy, negatively affects the investor's reputation, prevent the continuity of the project. Liquidity risk management includes these main measures: creating financial reserves, detailed cash flow planning, securing credit lines, insuring projects against financial disruptions.

d) Inflation risk and the impact on investments

Inflation risk is related to the general increase in prices in the economy, which reduces the purchasing power of money and increases the operational costs of the project.

Inflation has a negative impact by: increasing the cost of materials and services, reducing the real value of income, reducing the investor's real profit. This risk is particularly pronounced in long-term infrastructure projects. Inflation risk management is achieved through: indexing contracts according to inflation including an inflation reserve in the budget, using insurance for cost increases, periodic review of the financial plan.

e) Operational risks

Operational risks stem from the organization's internal processes and include technical failures, equipment problems, human errors, lack of qualified human resources or interruptions in the supply chain.

f) Legal and regulatory risks.

Changes in fiscal, financial and regulatory legislation, as well as non-compliance with contracts or legal rules, constitute significant risks for investment projects, especially in the international context.

g) Political and macroeconomic risks

Political risks are related to political instability, changes in government policies, conflicts and the risk of nationalization of assets. These risks are particularly pronounced in foreign direct investments.

1.5.2 Assessing the financial impact of the risk

When identifying risks, the next step is to assess their financial impact. This process aims to analyze the probability of each risk occurring and the magnitude of the potential loss it could cause.

Qualitative risk analysis. Qualitative analysis involves classifying risks according to their importance and impact on the project (low, medium and high risk). This analysis helps determine priorities for intervention.

Quantitative risk analysis. Quantitative analysis uses financial and statistical methods to measure the concrete impact of risk. Among the most commonly used methods are: sensitivity analysis, scenario analysis, financial simulations. These methods help assess the impact of risk on the project's financial indicators, such as net present value (NPV), internal rate of return (IRR) and cash flows.

1.5.3 Impact on financial decision-making

The results of risk analysis directly affect decisions to accept or reject the project, the financing structure and the choice of hedging instruments. Taking preventive measures for risk management aims to reduce the probability of risk occurrence or minimize its financial consequences.

- Diversification represents a basic risk management strategy, by distributing investments across sectors, markets and different financial instruments.

- Continuous control and monitoring, establishing internal control systems and periodic risk monitoring help in early identification of problems and taking corrective measures in time.

- Careful financial planning and ensuring sufficient liquidity help in coping with unforeseen situations and maintaining the financial stability of the project.

1.5.4 Transfer of risk to the insurer

Transfer of risk through insurance consists in passing the financial burden of possible losses from the investor to the insurance company, against the payment of an insurance premium.

Investment projects, especially those with high capital and high risk (e.g. construction, infrastructure, energy, important industries), are exposed to a number of risks that can negatively affect the achievement of financial and operational objectives. Insurance is one of the main tools for managing and transferring risk, enabling protection against unforeseen losses.

1.6 Types of insurance in investment projects

a) Property and equipment insurance.

This type of insurance covers material damage to the physical assets of the project, such as buildings, machinery, technical equipment and construction infrastructure. The insurance covers damage from natural disasters (fire, flood, landslide, earthquake). It provides for the repair or replacement of damaged equipment and assets. It often also includes business interruption as a result of material damage.

b) Civil liability insurance.

This insurance covers the investor's legal liability to third parties for material or personal damage that may occur during the implementation of the project. Liability for damage to persons or property of third parties is covered. It includes damage to the environment or legal consequences of accidents during work. Civil liability insurance helps avoid costly litigation.

c) Political risk insurance.

This insurance covers risks related to political instability and state intervention, which are among the main concerns for foreign investors in long-term infrastructure and energy projects (Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency, 2023; United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, 2022). These risks include confiscation or expropriation of assets by the host government, legal and regulatory changes that hinder or prohibit the operation of the project, and broader political instability that increases uncertainty and reduces the security of foreign investments (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2021). Political risk insurance is specifically designed to protect investors against financial losses resulting from such government actions or political events, ensuring continuity and financial protection of investments (World Bank, 2020).

d) Credit and financial guarantee insurance This type of insurance covers financial risks, including non-payment by contractual partners, payment delays or defaults by creditors. It ensures liquidity and cash flows for the project. It increases the security of investors and creditors. It serves as a guarantee for bank financing and contractual agreements.

1.7 The role of insurance in increasing project credibility

a) Insurance and investor confidence Investors are more willing to commit capital to insured projects, as these projects have clear risk coverage, reduce the probability of large losses and provide financial stability (Doherty, 2000; OECD, 2018). For institutional investors, insurance is not simply an operational cost, but a strategic instrument that increases the credibility, transparency and security of the investment, improving the risk-return profile of the project (World Bank, 2019).

b) Improving access to credit Banks and financial institutions consider insured projects to be less risky, as there is a formal mechanism for transferring risk to insurance and reinsurance companies (Swiss Re, 2022). This has concrete impacts: interest rates on loans are lower, repayment terms are more flexible and opportunities for securing additional funds increase (OECD, 2018). In this way, insurance helps the investor to manage financing more efficiently and improve the capital structure (World Bank, 2019).

c) Ensuring project continuity In the event of a risk (accident, natural disaster, financial disruption), insurance provides funds for repair or return to operation, enabling the project to be completed according to plan and reducing the risk of interruption of activity (Doherty, 2000). According to Swiss Re reports, 2022, reinsurance mechanisms play an essential role in coping with large catastrophic losses, ensuring financial stability even in high-impact scenarios.

d) Other benefits of credibility Insurance contributes to maintaining the reputation of the investor and the project in the market, improves relations with strategic partners and public authorities, and facilitates the negotiation of future contracts and international collaborations (OECD, 2018). Furthermore, transparency in risk management and the existence of insurance coverage increase institutional trust and the long-term sustainability of investments (World Bank, 2019).

1.8 Benefits of insurance for investors

a. The role of insurance in investment projects In investment projects, especially in capital-intensive sectors such as construction, infrastructure, energy and industry, investors face a wide range of financial, technical and operational risks. Insurance is one of the main instruments of risk management and transfer, playing a fundamental role in protecting the financial interests of investors. Through insurance, the investor reduces exposure to unforeseen losses and creates safer conditions for the realization of the long-term objectives of the project. For this reason, insurance is not just an additional cost, but a strategic investment in financial stability and continuity.

b. Protection of invested capital Invested capital represents the main financial source of the project and includes investor funds, bank loans and other sources of financing. Any unforeseen event that causes material damage, work interruptions or financial losses constitutes a direct threat to this capital. Insurance provides direct protection of capital through: compensation for material damage, coverage of financial losses, preservation of the value of the investment over time.

Practical example: In the case of an infrastructure construction project, damage to equipment or construction works by natural disasters can cause significant financial losses. By insuring the project, the investor avoids the need for additional financing and preserves the initial capital.

c. Financial security for investors Financial security is closely related to the investor's ability to predict cash flows and meet the financial obligations of the project. Insurance contributes to this by: limiting the maximum possible losses, guaranteeing financial compensation in the event of damage, stabilizing the financial balance of the project. In this way, the investor is able to better manage liquidity and maintain financial equilibrium.

d. Impact on financial planning An insured project offers safer conditions for planning: periodic payments, debt service, profit distribution. This significantly reduces the risk of financial crises during the investment life cycle.

e. Better financing opportunities Insurance as a condition for bank financing. Financial institutions, especially banks and investment funds, consider insurance as a fundamental condition for project financing. An insured project: is considered less risky, has a lower probability of failure, offers additional guarantees to creditors. As a result, investors benefit from: more favorable interest rates, longer repayment terms, more flexible credit conditions. An example in practice: In Albania, financing of infrastructure and construction projects usually requires construction insurance and civil liability insurance. Banks consider this insurance as a key element in assessing credit and financial risk

f. Continuity of projects One of the main benefits of insurance for investors is the guarantee of project continuity, even in the presence of unexpected events. Insurance enables the repair or reconstruction of damaged assets, provides funds for the resumption of works, avoids project abandonment. Without insurance, a severe event can lead to permanent project interruption and total loss of investment.

g. Impact on the investor's reputation The continuity of the project also positively affects the investor's reputation towards: strategic partners, financial institutions, public authorities. An investor who guarantees the completion of projects is considered more reliable and more competitive in the market.

h. Reducing uncertainty and risk management Uncertainty is one of the main factors that negatively affect investment decision-making. Insurance helps to: transfer risk from the investor to the insurer, reduce financial uncertainty, increase confidence in the implementation of the project. This allows investors to focus on the strategic and operational aspects of the investment.

i. Impact on investment decision-making. Insured projects: have a higher financial assessment, have a higher probability of implementation, are more attractive to new investors. As a result, insurance has a positive impact on investment growth and economic development.

2. INTERNATIONAL INSURANCE COMPANIES (GLOBAL ASPECT)

2.1 Providing coverage for very large projects

International insurance companies have the financial and technical capacity to cover projects that require insurance with extremely high values. Infrastructure and energy projects: For example, the construction of hydroelectric power plants, highways or energy networks requires large capital and coverage for various risks, from accidents, natural disasters to engineering errors. International companies can offer special policies that cover many types of risks simultaneously. Transnational project insurance: When a project involves many countries (e.g. the construction of gas pipelines that pass through several countries), international companies can offer unified coverage for the entire project, eliminating the need to negotiate with local insurers in each country.

Financial advantage: For very large projects, the risks are high and a large capital is required to cover them. International companies have the financial reserves and capacity to guarantee the payment of large claims in the event of fatal events.

Concrete examples: Providing coverage for very large projects. (Allianz,2025), coverage for infrastructure and engineering projects.

International companies such as Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty (AGCS) specialize in insuring large construction and infrastructure projects worldwide. AGCS offers insurance policies for construction risks, business interruption, contractor equipment, machinery damage, material transportation and complex infrastructure projects. These solutions are specifically designed for sectors such as energy, mining, transportation, civil projects and industrial construction, providing financial coverage for risks that are beyond the capabilities of most local insurers. For example, providing work interruption and loss of profit when a project is delayed due to an unexpected risk is a critical element in insurance contracts for large projects. These offerings also include coverage for various risks associated with complex technologies and construction processes.

AIG (American International Group (AIG) is one of the largest global insurers, operating in over 200 countries and jurisdictions, and offers a wide range of insurance that includes coverage for major international projects) – global solutions for international projects and programs AIG has multinational insurance programs (Multinational Insurance Solutions) that help companies operating in many countries have consistent and well-coordinated policies in each market. These solutions are especially important for companies with complex cross-border projects or with large insurance needs, where local insurance is not enough.

2.2 Global risk spreading

One of the main roles of international insurance companies is the ability to spread risk globally. Risk diversification: By operating in many markets and sectors, companies can balance losses from one region with profits from another. For example, losses from a natural disaster in Asia can be offset by profitable projects in Europe or America.

Global reinsurance network

International companies often use agreements with global reinsurers. This allows them to cover parts of the risk that are too large to be managed by the original company alone. Benefit for customers: For businesses with operations in many countries, this risk distribution reduces the possibility that a local event will cause catastrophic losses and increases financial stability.

Concrete example: SIGAL INSURANCE GROUP. Through reinsurance, local insurers transfer part of the risk to international companies such as Munich Re, Swiss Re, AXA, Allianz, Zurich or Lloyd's, increasing the total financial capacity to withstand large losses. This global distribution stabilizes the insurance market by reducing the risk for each individual actor and ensuring that extreme events (natural or otherwise) do not cause insurers to fail.

Example with Swiss Re. Swiss Re, one of the world's largest reinsurance companies, is working to use data and advanced technologies such as AI to develop new risk transfer instruments and offer stronger financial capacity to international clients and partners. This collaboration with new technology platforms aims to develop innovative risk placement and transfer instruments.

2.3 Advanced technical and financial expertise

International insurance companies do not only provide money for coverage, but also high technical and financial expertise that is essential for risk management.

Risk assessment: They use sophisticated actuarial models and advanced analytics to assess the probability of losses and determine optimal insurance costs.

Financial consulting: For large investment projects, these companies provide recommendations on financing structuring, ways to protect against financial risks and other insurance instruments such as complex policies or insurance derivatives.

Technology and innovation: International companies invest in technology for risk monitoring, data analysis and catastrophe prediction, giving clients more accurate and effective coverage.

Concrete example: AIG offers advanced risk management services, including consulting, risk analysis, and customized solutions that help organizations optimize the way they protect assets and reduce potential losses. Allianz Commercial also offers risk consulting and other solutions that include objective analysis and advice for better risk management in client businesses.

Preparation and training of specialists. Large international companies invest in staff training, the use of cutting-edge technology (e.g. AI) and the development of new risk analysis models to improve technical capacity and decision-making capabilities, which gives them a competitive advantage in global markets. Why do large projects use international insurance companies? Large projects (infrastructure, energy, industrial and construction) often require insurance that exceeds the capacities of local insurers, so they use companies with experience and global capacity.

2.4 Why do large projects use international insurance companies?

a. Higher financial capacity

The financial capacity of an insurance company is the amount of capital it can deploy to cover large losses from a single risk or a series of events. International companies have much larger capital than local insurers, which allows them to cover projects worth hundreds of millions or billions. Why does this matter for large projects? Large infrastructure projects (such as the construction of national roads, hydroelectric power plants, seaports, etc.) pose extremely high financial risks if something goes wrong (e.g. natural disaster or technical failure). International insurers such as Munich Re, Swiss Re, Allianz or AIG have the financial capacity to withstand these losses without risking the collapse of the insurance company.

b. Broader insurance coverage

This is important because large projects are not exposed to just one risk (e.g. fire), but face a wide range of interconnected risks. The literature on risk management emphasizes that infrastructure and industrial projects are characterized by multiple exposures to natural hazards (earthquakes, floods), engineering errors, technical failures, third-party liability, business interruption and financial losses (Doherty, 2000; World Bank, 2019).

According to reinsurance industry analyses, the increase in technological complexity and global interconnectedness has significantly increased the interdependence of risks, causing a single event to produce chain reactions in different economic sectors (Swiss Re, 2022). For this reason, modern insurance practices promote an approach of integrated and combined risk coverage (integrated risk coverage), instead of fragmented insurance.

Global insurance and reinsurance companies play a key role in managing the complex risks of large projects. For example, Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty (AGCS) offers multidimensional insurance packages that combine coverage for property damage, civil liability, business interruption, engineering risk and financial risk in a single policy (AGCS, 2021). This comprehensive approach increases the financial security of the project and facilitates access to financing, as creditors and investors require clear risk transfer mechanisms (OECD, 2018).

c. Credibility for foreign investors

Foreign investors (investment funds, international banks, multilateral organizations, energy companies, etc.) require assurance that their investment will be protected in the event of risk. International insurance companies are well-known and accepted in global markets and therefore increase the credibility of the project.

1-First, they offer: International insurance standards that are widely known and accepted by investors and banks;

2-Transparent reporting and control according to world practices;

3-Policies with clear conditions and a high level of payment in case of damage

Foreign investors often require that the insurance be done with companies with high credit ratings (e.g. Standard & Poor's, Moody's), such as Swiss Re or Allianz, as this increases the chances that the insurer will be able to pay even in the most difficult cases.

How does this relate to Albania? Even projects of Albanian companies seeking financing from international institutions (e.g. World Bank or EBRD financing) often need to have insurance with companies with a global reputation, otherwise investors may refuse the financing. This reflects a common practice in international project finance markets.

d. Acceptance by banks and financial institutions

When a bank provides loans for large projects (e.g. signing loan contracts for an energy project), it requires credit security that will allow the return of funds even in the event of a financial risk or unexpected event. Banks and financial institutions more readily accept insurance policies from international companies because they are rated according to international standards and have a proven reputation for liquidity and prompt payments. Without insurance from a strong international insurer, the bank may refuse to provide the loan or require additional interest rates and strict conditions, which makes the project less attractive for investment. This is also a common practice in Albania: when a project requires bank financing (which may be supervised by the Financial Supervisory Authority), banks often require that the insurance be acceptable to both financial regulators and foreign standards, to ensure that their risk is minimal.

2.5 International standards and practices in insurance

a. Implementation of international insurance standards

International insurance companies play a crucial role in capital projects and large financings, not only for financial capacity, but also for the implementation of global standards, transparency and unified contracts. These elements are crucial for ensuring the credibility and acceptability of projects by investors and banks.

They implement globally recognized standards that regulate the way risk is assessed, premiums are set and claims are paid. These standards ensure that each project is managed according to actuarial and financial insurance principles, reducing risk for clients and investors. Concrete examples: Swiss Re: Implements advanced risk assessment standards and reports according to international practices, using statistical models and simulations to predict losses.

Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty (AGCS): Uses Solvency II, an EU regulation that guarantees sufficient financial coverage and transparency in risk reporting. AIG: Provides detailed risk analysis for international projects and uses global standards to determine premium levels and coverages. In Albania: The Devoll solar energy project or the Vjosa hydropower plant uses international insurance from Allianz or AIG, to ensure

that risk and capital management standards comply with the requirements of international banks and financial institutions.

b. Transparency and strict regulations

International companies are required to report transparently on capital, reserves and risk management strategies. Strict regulations require insurers to follow clear procedures for claims payment, external audits and financial reporting according to international standards (e.g., IFRS – International Financial Reporting Standards). Concrete examples: Swiss Re and Allianz: Publish annual reports on financial capacity, risk exposure and protection strategies. This transparency is essential for investors and banks financing large projects. AIG: Ensures that any insurance contract for international projects is clearly documented and complies with the laws of the countries where the project operates, including periodic transparency audits. In Albania: For projects financed by the EBRD, the World Bank or KfW, the use of international insurers guarantees that all risk and damage reporting is transparent and acceptable to international financial institutions. This level of transparency also helps in the control of public funds and increases citizens' trust in the management of infrastructure projects. In conclusion: Transparency and strict regulations reduce risk for investors and strengthen the credibility of projects.

c. Unified international contracts

International insurance contracts are standardized to ensure complete clarity on coverages, responsibilities and claim payment procedures. The use of unified contracts helps companies and investors from different countries to have the same understanding of the agreement. Concrete examples: Allianz Global Corporate & Specialty: Offers standard policies for infrastructure projects in more than 70 countries, using unified documents that facilitate international cooperation.

Lloyd's of London: Uses globally recognized contracts for the insurance of capital and high-risk projects, including natural and industrial risk.

In Albania: When a project such as the Milot-Balldren highway or the Devoll hydropower plant receives financing from an international bank, international insurance contracts are unified and acceptable to all parties: banks, insurers and Albanian authorities. This ensures that each party clearly knows its rights and responsibilities, reducing disputes and potential delays. Thus, unified international contracts facilitate global cooperation, increase credibility and ensure clear risk management.

2.6 Reinsurance and its importance

Reinsurance is a key instrument of the insurance industry, allowing insurance companies to manage large risks, spread losses and have financial stability. It is particularly important for capital projects, local insurers and global markets.

a. Insuring insurance companies against large losses

Reinsurance functions as insurance for insurers. The insurance company transfers part of the risks to a reinsurance company. In case of unexpected events that

cause very large damages (earthquakes, floods, major fires), the insurer does not face catastrophic losses, because a part of them is covered by reinsurance.

Concrete examples: Swiss Re and Munich Re cover the risk for insurers operating in infrastructure and energy projects worldwide. For example, after the earthquake in Haiti (2010), many local insurers had international reinsurance that helped them pay the damages without going bankrupt. In Albania: Companies like SIGAL UNIQA Group Austria use reinsurance with international partners like Munich Re and Swiss Re to cover large losses, especially for property, vehicle and infrastructure insurance. In conclusion: Reinsurance ensures that insurers do not fail financially in case of extreme events and maintains the stability of the insurance market.

b. Reducing risk for local insurers

Local insurers usually have limited capital, so they cannot afford very large losses from a single event or a series of related events. By using reinsurance, local insurers spread the risk among international companies and thus reduce the risk for themselves and their clients. Concrete examples: SIGAL UNIQA in Albania: Uses international reinsurance for property and capital projects insurance, ensuring that an unexpected event (e.g.

flood or industrial fire) will not endanger the company's capital. Global example: In the United States, small insurers often use reinsurance from Lloyd's of London or Swiss Re to cover natural catastrophe risk. Bottom line: Reinsurance allows local insurers to offer greater and safer coverage to their clients, increasing the credibility of the industry.

c. Engaging global insurance markets

Reinsurance connects local insurers to global markets, where much of the capital and expertise is located abroad. International reinsurance companies provide capital, expertise and risk management models that are not available in local markets.

Concrete examples: Swiss Re and Munich Re operate in over 150 countries and provide reinsurance to local insurers on all continents, connecting them to global capital. Albania: SIGAL UNIQA and INSIG use international reinsurance partners, connecting them to global markets and ensuring that they can handle large capital projects, such as hydroelectric plants or industrial construction. This practice of engaging in global markets increases the liquidity, stability and credibility of local companies. In conclusion: Reinsurance is a bridge between local insurers and international capital, allowing capital projects and foreign investments to be protected from major risks.

Chart 1. Global reinsurance market (worldwide)

- \$900 billion – Global gross reinsurance premiums in 2023: According to the report of the International Association of Insurance Supervisors (IAIS), the global reinsurance market is around \$900 billion³. Reflecting a significant increase in activity in this sector.

About 13% of global insurance premiums are reinsurance premiums, indicating that a significant part of the world's risk is transferred from insurers to reinsurers.

³ IAIS -International Association of Insurance Supervisors (IAIS)

Chart 2. Regional composition of gross reinsurance premiums

• The chart 2 shows the regional composition of gross reinsurance premiums, broken down into life and non-life reinsurance⁴. About 35% of reinsurance premiums are life reinsurance, while 65% are non-life/catastrophe reinsurance. The split is most pronounced in Europe and Africa (17% life, 83% non-life), while it is equally pronounced in the Americas (49% life, 51% non-life). This shows the great importance of reinsurance in coverage of natural and industrial risks.

❖ **Albania Insurance Market 2025**

For 2025, gross premiums in the insurance market in Albania reached 20.18 billion lek, marking an increase of 10.37% compared to the same period last year.

The market remains oriented towards non-life insurance, which accounted for 91.69% of the total premium volume, while life insurance 8.27% and reinsurance 0.033%. In the Albanian market, reinsurance constitutes a very small part of the total insurance activity, unlike developed markets where about 1/5 of the risk is transferred to reinsurance, (Statistic Albania, 2023 xprimm).

2.7 Political risk insurance

a. Protection from legal and political changes

One of the main functions of political risk insurance is to protect against unexpected legal and political changes that may directly affect the investor's economic activity (Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency [MIGA], 2022). Political Risk Insurance (PRI) is considered a key instrument for managing exposure to sovereign risks and state interventions that undermine foreign investment (World Bank, 2020).

In many countries, especially in developing countries or those with political instability, state laws and policies can change frequently, without warning and without taking into account the interests of foreign investors. The literature on foreign direct investment highlights that institutional uncertainty and political risk are among the main factors influencing the decision-making of international investors (OECD, 2019).

These changes can have serious financial consequences, including loss of revenue, increased operating costs, and violation of contractual rights (MIGA, 2022).

These changes may include:

- sudden increases in taxes and duties (OECD, 2019)
- imposition of new customs duties (World Bank, 2020)
- restrictions on transferring profits abroad (MIGA, 2022)
- changes in labor laws (OECD, 2019)
- cancellation or non-renewal of licenses and permits (MIGA, 2022)
- prohibition of a certain economic activity for political or environmental reasons (World Bank, 2020)

Political risk insurance compensates for financial losses arising from these changes, including risks such as expropriation, restrictions on currency conversion and transfer, breach of contract by public authorities, and civil unrest (MIGA, 2022). In this way, it gives the investor a sense of security and stability, encouraging increased investment in markets with a higher level of institutional uncertainty (World Bank, 2020).

b. Coverage for nationalization, confiscation and war

One of the most serious risks that foreign investors face is direct state intervention in private property, which usually occurs in tense political situations, economic crises, regime changes or extreme ideologies. Political risk insurance is designed precisely to protect the investor from these extreme risks, which are often unpredictable and uncontrollable.

1. Nationalization

Nationalization occurs when the government of a country decides to take full control or ownership of a private investment, usually for political, economic or ideological reasons. This is often justified by the state as an action "in the public interest", but for the investor it represents a huge financial loss.

Nationalization usually affects:

- strategic industries (energy, oil, gas, mining)
- banks and financial institutions

⁴ GRMS- Global Reinsurance Market Survey

- telecommunications
- infrastructure
- agriculture and land

In many cases, the state does not offer any compensation for the property taken, or offers a symbolic compensation that does not reflect the real value of the investment, while there are also cases when the payment of compensation is delayed for many years, causing the investor significant financial losses and ongoing uncertainty. In these circumstances, political risk insurance plays a very important role, as it protects the investor's initial capital, compensates for losses of property taken from the state, and also covers the loss of expected profits that the investor was unable to realize. Thanks to this insurance, the investor gains security and confidence to enter and operate in uncertain markets, significantly reducing the risk of major financial losses.

2. Confiscation

Confiscation is an even more aggressive form of state intervention, where private property is taken without respecting legal procedures or the law is used as a political tool to drive away the investor.

Confiscation can occur in various forms:

- seizing property without a court order
- freezing bank accounts
- prohibiting access to business premises
- taking administrative control over the company
- restricting the right to sell or transfer property

Often, confiscation directly targets foreign investors and is used as a means of political pressure, while also being associated with corruption and a lack of transparency in decision-making. In these conditions, political risk insurance is of particular importance, as it compensates for financial losses caused by confiscation, covers cases when the investor loses real control over his business and offers protection even in situations where laws formally exist, but are not implemented fairly. Thanks to this insurance, the investor has the opportunity to avoid bankruptcy and more easily cope with the economic consequences of unjust state interventions.

3. War, civil unrest and political instability

Wars and civil unrest are among the most destructive factors for economic activity. They create complete uncertainty and often lead to a total cessation of investments.

These risks include:

- civil or international war
- coup d'état
- violent protests
- destabilization of public order
- political terrorism

These events can lead to the destruction of property, the interruption of production, the loss of markets and the inability to continue economic activity. Political risk insurance covers these losses, compensating for material and financial damages and helping the investor to cope with the consequences of political crises and ensure the financial continuity of the investment.

4. Political risk insurance necessary for investments made abroad

Investments abroad represent a great opportunity for profit, but at the same time a very high level of risk, especially in countries with fragile political stability. For this reason, political risk insurance is considered a key element of the international investment strategy.

- Why are investments abroad more risky?

Investments abroad are riskier because the foreign investor often does not have full knowledge of local laws and regulations, has no influence on political decision-making processes and does not enjoy direct institutional support in the host country. Furthermore, he faces cultural and administrative barriers, which can make communication, management and implementation of investment projects difficult. On the other hand, many host countries frequently change their economic policies, have ineffective judicial systems and are characterized by high levels of corruption, which creates constant uncertainty. Under these conditions, equal protection for foreign investors is not always guaranteed, making investing abroad a riskier and more uncertain process.

- The role of insurance in international investments

In this context, political risk insurance is essential because it significantly reduces uncertainty and financial risk. This insurance allows investors to plan long-term projects, protect their capital and avoid unexpected losses that could lead to bankruptcy. Moreover, many international banks and financial institutions require the existence of this insurance as a condition for financing projects abroad, making it an essential element in the investment process.

- Wider economic impact

Political risk insurance brings benefits not only to the investor, but also to the host country. It encourages the entry of foreign capital, increases the confidence of international markets and contributes to economic development, the creation of new jobs and the improvement of infrastructure. In this way, political risk insurance serves as a bridge between the interests of investors and the economic stability of host countries.

2.8 Cooperation with banks and financial institutions

Cooperation with banks and financial institutions constitutes one of the main pillars of the implementation of investment projects, especially when it comes to high-value investments or investments that are carried out outside national borders. Banks and financial institutions operate on the basis of risk assessment and capital security, therefore, every project that requires financing must meet certain conditions to guarantee stability and return on investment. In this context, insurance plays a crucial role in building trust and reducing financial uncertainty.

a) Insurance as a condition for loans and financing

In banking and financial practice, insurance is often a mandatory condition for granting loans and financing, especially for large infrastructure, industrial projects or for investments in countries with high political and economic risk. Before approving a loan, banks analyze in detail the risks that may negatively affect the borrower's ability to repay financial obligations. If the

risk is assessed as high, the bank requires additional security measures, among which insurance is one of the most important.

Project insurance guarantees the bank that, even in the event of unforeseen events such as major political changes, confiscation of assets, interruption of activity or civil unrest, financial losses will be partially or fully covered by the insurer. This significantly reduces the risk of non-repayment of the loan and makes the project more eligible for financing.

b) Guarantee for the stability of the project

Insurance serves not only as financial protection, but also as a guarantee for the stability and continuity of the project throughout its life cycle. Investment projects, especially long-term ones, are exposed to a number of risks that may arise at different stages, such as construction, operation or expansion. Without a protective mechanism, a single negative event can lead to the complete termination of the project.

When a project is insured, the investor and financial institutions have more confidence that the project will be sustainable even in difficult conditions. Insurance helps maintain liquidity, because financial compensation can be used to repair damages, continue activity or meet obligations to banks and suppliers. In this way, insurance contributes to protecting the interests of all parties involved and ensuring the long-term success of the project.

c) Support for foreign direct investment

Insurance plays a key role in promoting and supporting foreign direct investment, which is a very important source for the economic development of host countries. Foreign investors are often exposed to political, legal and institutional risks, which can discourage the entry of foreign capital. In this context, insurance serves as a mechanism that significantly reduces the fear of large losses and creates a more favorable environment for investment.

Through insurance, foreign investors feel more confident about investing in long-term projects, bringing not only financial capital, but also technology, professional knowledge and modern management practices. International financial institutions often cooperate with insurers and local governments to support these investments, creating more stable financial structures. As a result, insurance helps to increase the confidence of international markets, strengthen economic stability and promote sustainable development.

2.9 Advantages of insurance for the economy and foreign investment

a) Increased foreign investment

One of the most important benefits is the increase in foreign direct investment (FDI), which constitutes a major source of capital for host countries (World Bank, 2020). Foreign investors are often cautious about placing capital in new countries due to political, legal and economic uncertainty; however, when there is political risk insurance and support from international financial institutions, these investments become safer and more

acceptable (Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency [MIGA], 2022).

Increased foreign investment brings a series of benefits: foreign capital can be used to expand existing industries, open new businesses and stimulate innovative sectors (OECD, 2019). It also brings new knowledge and technologies, improving the efficiency and productivity of domestic companies. International companies often transfer advanced technologies and modern management practices, increasing the competitiveness and quality of products in the domestic market (OECD, 2019).

Foreign investments create jobs and increase the state's fiscal revenues, contributing to sustainable economic development. Without mechanisms for insurance and protection against political risk, many investors would be reluctant to enter markets with high institutional uncertainty, limiting long-term economic development (MIGA, 2022).

b) Economic stability

Economic stability is another essential benefit derived from political risk insurance and cooperation with financial institutions. When investors feel protected and have the certainty that their projects will not be damaged by political or unpredictable factors, this helps maintain the continuity of economic activity and prevents sudden capital crises.

Economic stability is important because it allows the government and economic actors to plan for the long term. It creates conditions for stable fiscal and monetary policies and increases market confidence. For example, a country with high political and legal stability is more likely to attract large infrastructure or technology investments because investors feel protected and confident about the return on capital.

A stabilized economy also helps reduce the risk of unpredictable inflation, currency devaluation, and banking sector collapse. This creates a more trustworthy environment for all companies, domestic and foreign, and can stimulate economic activity and production in a sustainable manner.

c) Infrastructure project development

Securing and protecting investments does not only help individuals or companies, but has a major impact on the development of infrastructure projects, which are the basis for the country's economic development. Projects such as the construction of roads, bridges, dams, electricity, water supply, public transport or telecommunications require large investments and are often exposed to political and economic risks.

When investors have protection from risks, they are more willing to commit significant capital and invest in long-term projects. These infrastructure projects improve the quality of life of citizens, increase the efficiency of the economy and facilitate the flow of goods and services. For example, a developed and maintained road network facilitates trade, reduces transportation costs and increases competition between businesses.

Furthermore, infrastructure development stimulates other economic sectors, such as construction, energy, logistics and tourism. Investments in this area have a ripple effect, positively impacting many areas of the economy and creating new jobs and development opportunities for local communities (MIGA, 2022).

Conclusions

From the assessment and analysis of factors that affect the insurance of investment projects of international companies, we reach several conclusions:

1. Insurance is a key element of risk management.

Investment project insurance functions as a fundamental mechanism for risk transfer and financial protection. It minimizes the consequences of natural, technical, operational, financial and political risks, ensuring stability and continuity for the project.

2. The role of insurance varies according to the project phases.

From planning to construction and operation, insurance adapts to the nature of the risks and the financial needs of the project. The construction phase requires CAR/EAR coverage, while the operation phase requires property, business interruption and civil liability insurance.

3. Political risk insurance plays a key role in protecting investors, especially in international investments, by reducing uncertainties related to legal changes, nationalization, confiscation and political instability.

4. Insurance of investment projects and investments of insurance companies play a key role in economic development and financial stability. Through effective risk management and investment diversification, insurance companies contribute to promoting investments and sustainable economic growth.

5. Insurance constitutes an essential element in protecting the interests of investors and in ensuring the success of investment projects. By protecting capital, providing financial security, improving access to financing, ensuring project continuity and reducing uncertainty, insurance becomes a strategic financial management mechanism.

6. In the context of developing economies such as Albania, the role of insurance becomes even more important in promoting sustainable and long-term investments. Investments are the foundation of the financial stability of insurance companies, and diversification and risk analysis are key to effective financial management. For our country, it is important to increase the share of investments in international markets, as well as the use of alternative instruments for increasing profits, implementing modern risk management tools.

7. The implementation of international standards guarantees that investors and lenders have high certainty about the return on capital and risk management, and transparency and strict regulations reduce the risk for investors and strengthen the credibility of projects.

8. Insurance increases financial and banking credibility.

Investors and banks use insurance to reduce financial risk and ensure the return on capital. This mechanism makes the project more acceptable for financing and reduces the probability of economic failure.

9. Insurance stimulates investment and economic development.

Protection from political, legal and financial risks increases the confidence of investors, especially foreign ones, stimulating direct investment and infrastructure development. This contributes to job creation and economic stability of the country.

10. Insurance companies such as Allianz etc. play a role not only in project insurance, but also in strategic capital investments for infrastructure, diversifying their economic portfolio.

Recommendations

1. Develop a clear insurance strategy for each phase of the project

Investors should analyze risks at the planning stage and determine the most appropriate types of insurance for construction, assembly and operation, including CAR, EAR and property insurance

2. Use of political insurance for investments abroad

International investments should be accompanied by political risk insurance that covers nationalization, confiscation and civil unrest, to reduce uncertainty and potential losses.

3. Strengthening the regulatory framework for insurance company investments

Improving the legislation on insurer investments, further harmonizing it with international standards, so that insurance companies have a clearer framework for diversifying their investment portfolio.

4. Recommendations for promoting investments in strategic and sustainable sectors

Encouraging insurance companies to invest in infrastructure and development projects, such as transport, energy and water supply and sewerage, which offer long-term and relatively stable returns. Using international insurance and reinsurance mechanisms to reduce the risk of investments in large projects and attract foreign capital.

5. Recommendations for increasing transparency and improving risk management

Implementation of international financial and risk reporting standards, as well as risk management standards, to increase the transparency of investment activities. Strengthening internal risk management systems, including the assessment of operational, financial and market risk for each insured investment project.

6. Active cooperation with banks and financial institutions

For high-value projects, insurance should be used as a tool to secure lending, guaranteeing banks for the return of capital and helping to structure the project in a financially sustainable manner.

7. Using insurance as a stimulus for economic and infrastructure development

Authorities and investors should encourage the use of insurance for large infrastructure projects, ensur-

ing that projects are sustainable even in crisis conditions and attract foreign capital for sustainable development.

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